

NAVIGATING THE TEACHING JOURNEY: CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISM OF PRACTICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms employed by practice teachers during the Second Semester of A.Y. 2024–2025 at Urdaneta City University. Utilizing a descriptive-quantitative research design, the study gathered data through survey questionnaires distributed to education interns. The descriptive method was used to analyze current situations, allowing the researchers to interpret findings related to physical, emotional, financial, and academic difficulties. The analysis revealed that physical and emotional challenges were most significant, particularly issues in classroom management, fatigue, and maintaining work-life balance. Financial constraints and limited academic preparedness, such as difficulty in using diverse teaching strategies and integrating technology, were also noted. Despite these, respondents demonstrated adaptability through both personal and academic coping strategies. Social support, particularly from mentors and family, emerged as the most relied-upon coping method, while pedagogical strategies such as effective communication and use of instructional materials were frequently used in academic contexts. The findings also indicated that specialization, age, and gender significantly influenced the nature of challenges and coping strategies, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in those variables. Practice teachers in physically demanding or conceptually complex subjects experienced more pronounced challenges. The study recommends implementing targeted wellness programs, financial support systems, enhanced mentorship, and specialized pedagogical training to address the varied needs of interns. The results emphasize the need for institutions to strengthen support

mechanisms to prepare future educators for the evolving demands of the teaching profession.

Keywords: *Practice Teaching, Coping Mechanisms, Challenges, Teaching Strategies, Mentorship, Teacher Education*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a long, challenging, yet rewarding process that involves attending classes, completing projects, taking examinations, and engaging in various school-related activities. For pre-service teachers enrolled in the College of Teacher Education, one of the most pivotal components of their academic journey is the practice teaching internship. Teaching Practice (TP) is a mandatory aspect of any teacher education program, serving as a platform for student-teachers to implement strategies and techniques learned during their academic coursework (Aldabbus, 2020). This phase of training allows pre-service teachers to apply pedagogical knowledge in actual classroom settings, preparing them for the real-world demands of the teaching profession.

According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 75, Series of 2017, Article IV Section 5, practice teaching is a required component for the completion of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) program. CHED Memorandum Order No. 104, Series of 2017, further emphasizes the need to safeguard the well-being, learning quality, and safety of higher education students during internship programs. Through practice teaching, student-teachers are exposed to experiential learning, wherein knowledge is constructed through exploration and active participation.

Despite its significance, practice teaching is accompanied by numerous challenges. Aldabbus (2020) noted that student-teachers face several significant hurdles, even when applying the skills acquired in college. Similarly, Kabeke (2021) emphasized that bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application remains a key concern during the practicum phase. Effective planning and execution are necessary to address these challenges, ensuring that teaching practice fulfills its intended role in teacher preparation.

To manage these difficulties, student-teachers often resort to coping strategies, which refer to the methods individuals use to address stressors in academic and classroom environments. Coping mechanisms may involve emotional regulation or problem-solving strategies. Algorani and Gupta (2023) defined coping as the intentional mobilization of ideas and behaviors to manage internal and external stressors, distinguishing it from unconscious defense mechanisms.

Internationally, various studies have highlighted the obstacles encountered by practice teachers. In Indonesia, Prastomo and Indonesia (2020) identified four major challenges: adapting to unfamiliar environments, dealing with student behavior and psychological issues, navigating relationships with mentor teachers, and lacking adequate content knowledge. In Thailand, classroom management, confidence, and

insufficient teaching tools were primary concerns (Deocampo, 2020; Junlakitjawat et.al, 2024; Ulla, 2016). These studies underscore the multifaceted nature of difficulties in teaching practicum.

In the Philippines, educators similarly face numerous stressors. Francisco et al. (2023) found that teachers in Leyte with ancillary duties experienced overwhelming responsibilities and burnout. Gonzales et al. (2023) reported that Senior High School teachers faced stress due to multiple subject preparations and extended working hours. To cope, teachers commonly rely on social support, collaboration, problem-solving, and positive thinking strategies (Francisco et al., 2023; Mapfumo et al., 2011).

Additional challenges were identified in Nigeria, where pre-service teachers in teaching practice programs experienced stress from multiple sources. While stress levels did not directly correlate with academic achievement, students employed coping strategies that could inform future training designs (Osiesi et al., 2023). In Pakistan, traditional teaching methodologies and lack of feedback mechanisms further impeded student-teachers' development (Siddiqui & Mughal, 2021; Naseem, 2022).

In the Philippine context, financial stress was highlighted as a major concern by Mina (2022), with other contributors including academic and familial pressures. Coping mechanisms ranged from spiritual practices to social support. Similarly, Mamauag (2022) noted that stressors during the pandemic included workload changes, new teaching modalities, and health concerns, with prayer being a prevalent coping method.

Other local studies identified issues such as time management, lesson preparation, classroom behavior, and lack of teaching resources (Dacanay et al., 2019). Castaño (2023) emphasized self-regulation and social support as common coping strategies in blended learning environments. Botona and Baguio (2025) recommended stress management programs, highlighting techniques such as problem-solving and self-control. Pedroso et al. (2023) supported these findings by identifying coping strategies like emotional support and goal-setting among student leaders. Collantes (2021) also noted issues such as uncooperative mentor teachers, noisy students, and limited resources.

Emerging literature also reveals how personal profile variables influence the challenges and coping mechanisms of student-teachers. Emeljanovas et al. (2023) found that financial stability and engaging hobbies helped mitigate psychological stress, whereas isolation and unhealthy habits heightened distress. McCallum et al. (2024) reported that less experienced teachers were more prone to anxiety due to job insecurity. Gender was also identified as a factor, with female student-teachers exhibiting higher levels of anxiety in supervised environments (Kanyarat & Kanyarat, 2022).

Regarding specialization, Donguines et al. (2021) observed no significant correlation between subject area and stress levels, suggesting that other factors may play a greater role in pre-service teacher experiences. Additionally, Mheidly et.al (2020) highlighted the mental toll of extended use of digital tools in online teaching, contributing to fatigue and burnout.

Given these insights, the researchers of this study recognized the need to examine whether there have been changes in the challenges and coping strategies commonly experienced by student-teachers, particularly in the context of recent academic years. This study seeks to determine the nature and extent of challenges and coping mechanisms among practice teachers during the Second Semester of A.Y. 2024–2025. By doing so, the study aims to deepen understanding of the evolving realities of practice teaching and contribute relevant data to guide future teacher education reforms and support systems. The findings are expected to enrich the existing body of knowledge and benefit a broader audience, including educators, mentors, and education policymakers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges and coping mechanisms of the respondents in their practice teaching during the Second Semester, A.Y. 2024-2025.

Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. Age,
 - b. Sex,
 - c. Specialization; and
 - d. Gadgets used in teaching?
 2. What are the challenges encountered by the Practice-Teacher in terms of:
 - 2.1 Personal Related;
 - a. Physical,
 - b. Emotional,
 - c. Social:
 - d. Financial?
 - 2.2 Academic related:
 - a. Technological Knowledge;
 - b. Pedagogical Knowledge; and
 - c. Content Knowledge?
 3. What are the coping mechanisms utilized by the practice teachers?
 4. Is there a significant difference between the challenges encountered by the respondents across their profile variables?
 5. Is there a significant difference between the coping mechanisms of the respondents across their profile variables?
 6. Based on the findings, what intervention measures can be proposed to address the challenges?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms by Practice-Teachers in their internships. Thus, it utilized the quantitative approach to have relevant and accurate information.

The quantitative approach emphasizes objective measurements and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of questionnaire data. It is concerned with collecting numerical data and generalizing it across groups of individuals or explaining a specific phenomenon (Babbie, 2010).

Specifically, it used the Descriptive-Quantitative approach. In quantitative research, the descriptive technique involves acquiring information on current facts or situations to describe and interpret them (Salaria, 2012).

Complete Enumeration

The respondents of this study were Fourth-year Practice-Teachers of the College of Teacher Education at Urdaneta City University (UCU), Academic Year 2024-2025—a total population of 282 Practice-Teachers with a Bachelor of Secondary and Elementary Education degree.

The researcher used a complete enumeration, in which the whole population of the enrolled 4th-year Practice- Teachers became the respondents of this study. The total number of respondents is 282, of which eleven (11) were from Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education, two (2) from Bachelor of Early Childhood Education, sixty (60) from Bachelor of Elementary Education, fifty-four (54) from Bachelor of Physical Education, sixty-nine (69) from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English, twenty-four (24) from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino, eighteen (18) from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science, fourteen (14) from Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics, twenty-seven (27) Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies, one (1) form Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in PEHM, two (2) from Bachelor of Special Needs Education with a total of two hundred eighty-two (282).

The table on the next page shows the distribution of 282 fourth-year College of Teacher Education Practice-Teachers according to their specialization.

Table 1
Number of Enrolled 4th Year Practice-Teachers in the College of Teacher Education

Programs	No. of Enrolled Students
<i>Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education</i>	11
<i>Bachelor of Early Childhood Education</i>	2
<i>Bachelor of Elementary Education</i>	60
<i>Bachelor of Physical Education</i>	54
<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English</i>	69

<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics</i>	14
<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino</i>	24
<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science</i>	18
<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies</i>	27
<i>Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in PEHM</i>	1
<i>Bachelor of Special Needs Education</i>	2
Total	282

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used a questionnaire checklist that distributed to the 4th-year practice teacher participants who undergoing practice teaching in their respective assigned schools.

A questionnaire checklist is a simple instrument that consists of a prepared list of expected items of performance or attributes that are checked for presence or absence by a respondent (Sonawane, 2022).

The questionnaire checklist comprises respondents' profiles regarding their age, sex, specialization, and gadgets. Next, the challenges faced by Practice-Teachers can be academic and personal. Also, the coping mechanisms that the respondents are using to manage the challenges they encounter.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher requested approval of the instrument for data collection from the three (3) experts. Upon approval, the researcher gathered information from the College of Teacher Education Practice-Teachers at Urdaneta City University, with 282 participants through the checklist questionnaire.

The questionnaire was accompanied by a letter outlining the purpose and objectives of the study for the respondents. The respondents were given ample time to respond to the inquiries to maintain a strategic distance from blunders and inaccuracies in their answers. The questionnaire checklist was personally distributed to the College of Teacher Education Practice-Teachers. After completing the survey questionnaire, the researcher collected, totaled, and examined the survey replies before interpreting the results.

Tools for Data Analysis

Several statistical treatments of data were utilized to answer the problems established in this study. To come up with a valid and reliable interpretation of data, the following statistical measures were used.

To answer problem number 1 on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, specialization, and gadgets used in teaching, frequency counts, and percentages will be used.

$$\text{Formula: AWM} = \frac{\sum f_i x_i}{n}$$

Where: AWM is the average weighted mean

f_i = frequency of each response

x_i = is the classification value of each category

n = is the total number of respondents

The weighted mean will be used to answer problem number two (2) regarding the challenges faced by the Practice-Teachers. It will be described using the scale below.

$$\text{Formula: AWM} = \frac{\sum f_i x_i}{n}$$

Where: AWM is the average weighted mean

f_i = frequency of each response

x_i = is the classification value of each category

n = is the total number of respondents

Point Value	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

To answer problem number three (3) on the coping mechanisms used by Practice-Teachers in their practice teaching, the weighted mean will be used. The formula is shown below:

$$\text{Formula: AWM} = \frac{\sum f_i x_i}{n}$$

Where: AWM is the average weighted mean

f_i = frequency of each response

x_i = is the classification value of each category

n = is the total number of respondents

Point Value	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

To answer problem number four (4) about the significant difference in the challenges faced by the respondents across their profile variables and problem number five (5) about the significant difference in their coping mechanisms across their profile variables, a t-test, and analysis of variance will be used using an open-source program.

To answer problem No.6, the researcher will develop intervention measures to address the challenges encountered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter concerns the data presentation of the study's findings. The findings are presented in both textual and tabular form, following the sequence of the specific research problem about the challenges Practice-Teachers face and their coping mechanisms.

Profile of the Respondents

In this section, the profile of the 282 Practice-Teachers in the College of Teacher Education who participated in this study. They were described in terms of the following demographic information: Age, sex, specialization, and gadgets used in teaching.

Table 1a
Demographic Profile in Terms of Age
N=282

PROFILE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Age	21	76	27.00
	22	142	50.40
	23	47	16.70
	24	8	2.80
	25	4	1.40
	26	3	1.10
	29	1	0.40
	34	1	0.40
	Total		282

Table 1a presents the demographic breakdown of 282 respondents categorized by age. Among them, a notable portion comprises 142 individuals aged 22, representing the highest frequency within the population.

The national educational framework currently comprises a comprehensive four-stage, 13-year curriculum encompassing Primary School, Intermediate School, Junior High School, and Senior High School. The anticipated age for graduation is around 18, coinciding with the transition to college. Consequently, individuals undertaking Teaching Internship courses, referred to as Practice-Teachers, typically reach the age of 22.

This age correlation is substantiated by the requirements outlined in CHED Memorandum Order No. 104 s. 2017, section 16 stipulates that student interns must attain a minimum age of eighteen (18) at the commencement of their internship period. Thus, the data obtained corroborates the observation that Practice-Teachers participating in the internship program are above the age threshold of 18.

Table 1b
Demographic Profile in Terms of Sex
N=282

PROFILE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Sex	Male	76	27.00
	Female	206	73.00
	Total	282	100.00

Regarding sex on the previous page, 76 or 27% are male, and 206 or 73% are female. This implies that most respondents who chose to undertake the teaching profession are female students. According to Sebastian et al. (2022), the teaching profession is still female-dominated, and students have limited encounters with male and father figures in Education.

Additionally, based on the World Bank (2021) statistics, the percentage of female secondary school teachers in the Philippines was reported to be 71.29%, and the rate of female primary school teachers in the Philippines was also recorded at 87.63%. This shows that the teaching profession is a female dominated course at present.

Table 1c
Demographic Profile in Terms of Specialization
N=282

PROFILE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE(%)
Specialization	BPEd	54	19.10
	BEEd	60	21.30
	BCAEd	11	3.90
	BSNEd	2	0.70
	BECEd	2	0.70
	BSEPEHM	1	0.40
	BSESOCSCI	27	9.60
	BSEMATH	14	5.00
	BSEFIL	24	8.50
	BSEENG	69	24.50
	BSEGENSCI	18	6.40
		Total	282

As shown in the table on the previous page, 24.50% of the respondents are from Bachelor of Secondary Education majors in English. This means that most respondents are currently taking teacher education courses with English as their specialization.

According to Imbat et al. (2023), perceived Competence and Career Opportunities and Rewards are two factors that impact English pre-service teachers' decisions regarding their area of specialization in the teacher education program. The participants emphasized that being exceptionally proficient in English has greatly influenced their decision to become pre-service English teachers. Also, pre-service English teachers have considered extrinsic variables like financial compensation or income and the assurance of a better future. Additionally, majoring in English can lead to various chances, such as the chance to work abroad because English is a universal language.

Table 1d
Demographic Profile in terms of Gadgets Used in Teaching
N=282

PROFILE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Gadgets used in teaching	Smartphone	200	70.90
	Laptop	249	88.30
	Tablet/Ipad	24	8.50
	Computer	19	6.70
	Others	9	3.20

Regarding gadgets used, laptops had the highest frequency, at 249 or 88.30%. This implies that 21st-century Practice-Teachers use laptops and various technologies as supportive tools for their internship tasks. Using a laptop meant having immediate access to multiple applications and other resources, connecting to other systems, sending and receiving connections via email and the internet, and expanding the classroom through improved usability and accessibility. Even though it is mainly used in the teaching process within the school, like presentations, laptops also make planning and preparation more effective.

According to Parr and Ward (2010), laptops were a necessary component of educational setup. Every instance of teaching and learning that was observed involved using laptops. Most importantly, laptops have become a hidden component of these educators' resources. It has become an indispensable teaching and learning tool in the digital world.

The second gadget commonly used by Practice-Teachers is a smartphone, with a percentage of 70.90% and a frequency of 200. Tablets and iPads follow, with a percentage of 8.50% and a frequency of 24. Next is the computer, with a percentage of 6.70% and a frequency of 19. Lastly, some respondents chose others, with a percentage of 3.20 and a frequency of 9.

Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers

The succeeding tables show the extent of challenges faced by respondents in terms of personal and academic difficulties. This indicates the vast number of challenges the respondents experience in their teaching internships.

A. Physical

Table 2.1a shows the extent of physical challenges faced by Practice-Teachers, with a weighted mean of 2.88, described as "Sometimes".

Table 2.1a
Personal Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Physical
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I had difficulties in managing noise levels in the classroom, which can lead to physical strain on my vocal cords or hearing.	3.44	S	1
2. I experienced physical fatigue due to long hours of standing and constant movement in the classroom.	3.11	S	2

3.	I encountered problems with organizing the classroom and managing resources, which resulted in physical discomfort due to the continuous bending, lifting, and carrying of materials.	2.69	S	8
4.	I had difficulty giving personalized attention to each student, which led to physical exhaustion from continuously moving around the classroom.	2.80	S	6
5.	I had trouble managing disruptive student behavior, which resulted in physical tension and stress.	2.80	S	7
6.	I experienced physical discomfort due to inadequate classroom temperature or poor ventilation.	2.92	S	5
7.	I faced physical strain from continuously bending to interact with students at their eye level.	2.40	R	10
8.	I encountered difficulties in managing time and completing tasks, leading to physical stress and exhaustion.	2.99	S	4
9.	I had difficulty maintaining and organizing the classroom environment which resulted in physical discomfort and fatigue.	2.65	S	9
10.	I faced physical strain from carrying heavy bags or materials for teaching, commuting, or attending professional development activities.	3.04	S	3
WEIGHTED MEAN		2.88	S	

Legend

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 1, "I had difficulties in managing noise levels in the classroom, which can lead to the physical strain on my vocal cords or hearing", obtained the highest mean of 3.44 and was described as "Sometimes". This implies that the noise level in the classroom environment is sometimes unmanageable to the point that it can lead to physical strain on the part of Practice-Teachers and distraction during the teaching and learning process. According to Bulunuz et al. (2021), loud noise levels in schools have been linked to teacher hypersensitivity, migraines, lengthy and severe headaches, tinnitus, communication difficulties, difficulty focusing on lessons, adverse effects on family communication and interaction, excessive fatigue, and distraction, a lowered tolerance limit, and feelings of exhaustion and rage. Therefore, noise does not only affect the teaching and learning process but also the physical health of Practice-Teachers.

Further, the second highest mean is Indicator 2, which was described as "Sometimes", which states that Practice-Teachers experience physical fatigue due to long hours of standing and constant movement in the classroom. This indicates that Practice-Teachers are more than just sitting in the school. Instead, they stand and perform constant movements like walking to catch the students' attention, which will benefit learning. Similarly, according to Alias et al. (2019), prolonged standing or static working posture is frequently observed in the classroom, particularly during school hours. Extended periods of static standing pose significant disadvantages, as an individual's lower extremities would be required to maintain their entire body weight. This will cause constant strain on the knee joints, particularly the feet and lower extremities, increasing the likelihood of pain and discomfort.

On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest mean was 7, "I faced physical strain from continuously bending to interact with students at their eye level", which was described as "Rarely". This means Practice-Teachers do not need to bend to maintain eye contact with the students. Eye contact is one of the most effective ways we communicate. A simple glance from across the classroom can say a lot. Eye contact communicates social information to the person we are listening to and speaking with. Moreover, it is critical for mutual understanding and classroom control (Gramatkovski & Kochoska, 2016). It does not mean that Practice-Teachers need to adjust themselves to the eye level of the students for them to learn because even from a distance, they can maintain eye contact with the students.

B. Emotional

Table 2.1b on the previous page reveals that Practice-Teachers face various challenges in terms of their emotional well-being, with a weighted mean of 2.84, indicating that these challenges are "Sometimes".

Among the listed indicators, Indicator 2, which pertains to balancing lesson planning, grading, and personal life, can be overwhelming. It received the highest mean of 3.49 and was also described as "Sometimes". This suggests that the overwhelming task of balancing these responsibilities is the number one challenge faced by Practice-Teachers. It signifies that Practice-Teachers struggle to balance their professional and personal obligations. The demanding nature of lesson planning and grading and the desire to maintain individual well-being can lead to overwhelming feelings and potential difficulties in achieving a healthy work-life balance. This challenge may impact their emotional well-being and overall performance satisfaction.

Table 2.1b
Personal Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Emotional
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I struggled with managing my emotions and maintaining a positive mindset in challenging situations.	2.98	S	3
2. Balancing lesson planning, grading, and personal life can be overwhelming.	3.49	S	1
3. I feel pressured to perform well and meet my expectations.	3.40	S	2
4. I experience difficulty managing my emotions in front of my students whenever I get too angry.	2.73	S	7
5. I find it difficult to interact with parents, especially in challenging situations.	2.59	S	8
6. I experience setbacks or feeling like lesson didn't go well.	2.86	S	4
7. I doubt my teaching abilities.	2.73	S	6
8. I experience hard time taking the constructive criticism and feedback from my cooperating teacher.	2.43	R	9
9. I find it hard to do my best at school because of the lack of support from my family.	2.42	R	10
10. I feel emotionally drained when trying to address the diverse need of students, including those with learning disabilities or behavioral issues.	2.78	S	5
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.84	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)

3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

The study conducted by Analazi (2019) highlights that lesson planning continues to be a significant challenge for Practice-Teachers. The transition from being a student to becoming a pre-service teacher and eventually an effective teacher is demanding in Education. This implies that Practice-Teachers need help in effectively planning and preparing lessons that cater to the diverse needs of their students. Thus, Practice-Teachers need help balancing lesson planning, grading, and personal life. The overwhelming nature of this task makes it the primary challenge Practice-Teachers face.

Meanwhile, indicator 9, "I find it hard to do my best at school because of the lack of support from my family", obtained the lowest mean of 2.42, which was categorized as "Rarely". This means that most of the Practice-Teachers' families fully support them during their internship. The study by Durlisic and Bunijevac (2017) further supports this interpretation by highlighting the significant impact parents and families have on the success of the Education and upbringing of children. When Practice-Teachers receive support from their families, it can positively influence their performance and well-being in the classroom. Having the support and encouragement of their families can contribute to Practice-Teachers' confidence, motivation, and overall performance satisfaction. It creates a supportive environment that allows them to focus on their professional growth and effectively fulfill their teaching responsibilities.

Moreover, it is also aligned with Nevitt Sanford's Theory of Challenge and Support since support is really needed for specific tasks. However, it should be balanced since too much support will lead to dependence, and too much reliance leads to stagnant performance.

A. Social

Table 2.1c presents the social challenges faced by Practice-Teachers, with a weighted mean of 2.51 indicating that these challenges occur "Sometimes".

Table 2.1c
Personal Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Social
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I received lack sense of belonging and support from my colleagues.	2.34	R	8.5
2. I experienced being disrespected by my students.	2.55	S	4
3. I had lack of confidence in instructional methods, lesson planning, and adapting to unforeseen circumstances due to my inexperience.	2.52	S	5
4. I experienced difficulty managing a classroom with diverse personalities, behaviors, and learning styles.	2.68	S	2
5. I experienced significant challenges when trying to communicate with students effectively.	2.70	S	1
6. I find it challenging to establish authority in the classroom, particularly when dealing with diverse groups of students.	2.67	S	3
7. I encountered difficulty on communicating effectively with parents and families of my students.	2.30	R	10

8. I struggled with building relationships and establishing rapport with students, especially when entering a new classroom or school environment.	2.46	R	7
9. I encountered difficulty in adapting the social dynamics and expectation of different grade levels or age groups of student.	2.51	S	6
10. I experienced isolation or a sense of being an outsider, particularly when working in a new school or community where I had limited connections.	2.34	R	8.5
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.51	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Among the listed indicators, Indicator 5, "I experienced significant challenges when trying to communicate with students effectively", gained the highest mean of 2.70, described as "Sometimes". This suggests that effective communication, be it written or oral, with students is one of the challenges practiced teachers face in the social aspect. It can be due to the language diversity existing in the teaching and learning process, which leads to the rise of barriers to communication. While enriching the classroom with various viewpoints, this diversity can make it difficult for the Practice-Teachers to ensure their message is accurately received and understood by all. Effective communication is crucial for building positive relationships, fostering a supportive classroom environment, and facilitating meaningful learning experiences. Practice-Teachers may face barriers in connecting with students, such as language barriers, cultural differences, diverse learning needs, or classroom management issues.

To relate, the study of Duta (2015) states that effective communication with students can be challenging because of a variety of factors, including a lack of resources for instruction, a lack of interaction, a lack of feedback, the distance that is created between teachers and students, physical, psychological, cognitive, and socio-political barriers. These challenges in communication can impact the overall teaching and learning process. Practice-Teachers may need help to convey information, engage students actively, and address individual student needs. It may also hinder the establishment of a positive teacher-student rapport, which is essential for creating a conducive learning environment.

Furthermore, indicator 7, "I encountered difficulty in communicating effectively with parents and families of my students", gained the lowest mean of 2.30 with a descriptive equivalent of "Rarely". Practice-Teachers generally experience fewer challenges when communicating with parents and families than in other aspects of social interaction because their cooperative teachers expect them to communicate directly with the student's parents. Practice-Teachers focus more on teaching and students' learning processes since they are still in the learning phase of the actual teaching profession.

An essential step in becoming a teacher is to practice teaching. It makes Practice-Teachers familiar with the actual teaching and learning environment. A student-teacher

can experience teaching in a classroom setting during teaching practice before entering the actual teaching field. Since teaching practice creates the actual bridge between student life and professional membership, student-teachers recognize its importance and consider it a crucial component of their preparation for the teaching profession (Rakesh Ranjan, 2013). It is also under the Experiential Learning Theory since practice teaching is when Practice-Teachers can have an experience in schools, which will help them gain knowledge and skills they can use once they become teachers. Thus, the main focus of Practice-Teachers is the practice teaching itself, and it does not include communicating with the students' parents. However, respondents can still participate in teacher and parent activities like meetings to observe and learn.

B. Financial

Table 2.1d on the next page, shows the extent of challenges faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of finances with a weighted mean of 2.82, described as "Sometimes".

Indicator 6, "I struggle to create a financial plan due to my unexpected expenses", gained the highest mean of 3.03 and was described as "Sometimes". This implies that managing and planning finances becomes more complicated when allocating money for unforeseen expenses. Practice-Teachers, especially those new to the profession, may need more experience in budgeting and financial planning. With prior knowledge and guidance on managing finances, they can effectively anticipate and prepare for unexpected expenses during internships. Similarly, Acedillo's (2018) study states that Practice-Teachers struggle with managing unexpected expenses. Practice-Teacher's financial management practices could be better, impacting their ability to handle such financial challenges effectively.

Table 2.1d
Personal Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Financial
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. 1. I don't have enough money to buy needed materials for my lesson/s.	2.72	S	7
2. 2. I experience paying a big amount for the high transportation fare.	2.99	S	2.5
3. 3. I find it hard to allocate the money given by my family/guardian.	2.82	S	5
4. 4. I don't have enough allowance for everyday expenses because of financial instability.	2.66	S	9
5. 5. I feel beaten down by money worries due to high prices of products.	2.99	S	2.5
6. 6. I struggle to create a financial plan due to my unexpected expenses.	3.03	S	1
7. 7. I experience difficulty in applying financial literacy.	2.79	S	6
8. 8. I compulsively buy unnecessary products leading to my insufficient allowance.	2.63	S	10
9. 9. I experience lack of funding to buy needed gadgets needed for the teaching process.	2.67	S	8
10. 10. I experience difficulty in my money matters due to personal needs.	2.94	S	4
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.82	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)

3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 6, "I struggle to create a financial plan due to my unexpected expenses", gained the highest mean of 3.03 and was described as "Sometimes". This implies that managing and planning finances becomes more complicated when allocating money for unforeseen expenses. Practice-Teachers, especially those new to the profession, may need more experience in budgeting and financial planning. With prior knowledge and guidance on managing finances, they can effectively anticipate and prepare for unexpected expenses during internships. Similarly, Acedillo's (2018) study states that Practice-Teachers struggle with managing unexpected expenses. Practice-Teacher's financial management practices could be better, impacting their ability to handle such financial challenges effectively.

Indicators 2 and 5 got the second highest mean of 2.99, described as "Sometimes". Indicator 2, "I experience paying a big amount for the high transportation fare", implies that Practice-Teachers allocate a large portion of their allowance to the transportation fare needed to go to their respective schools and end up compromising to fulfill other expenses. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), transport prices have increased dramatically by 14.6 percent yearly. The rate of increase "significantly outpaces the overall inflation". The PSA stated that one major cause of the increase was the continuous rise in oil prices, particularly for diesel, which is most widely used by drivers and operators of public utility vehicles (Peña, 2022).

Indicator 5, "I feel beaten down by money worries due to high prices of products", implies that Practice-Teachers are dealing with the effect of inflation, making it difficult for them to budget their allowance even for their necessities. According to De Jesus and De Jesus (2021), it was discovered that teachers spend the majority of their money on needs and rarely on miscellaneous and leisure activities. However, the inflation rate was the most common issue experienced by people when they were spending.

Lastly, indicator 8, "I compulsively buy unnecessary products leading to my insufficient allowance", had the lowest mean of 2.94, classified as "Sometimes". It suggests that the inflation rate is high, and there may be low buying capacity for Practice-Teachers, which is why they buy only the needed products for their internship. Moreover, Practice-Teachers understand the priorities they need during the internship. In the study conducted by Collantes (2021), the allowances of Practice-Teachers hardly covered their daily expenses for food and transportation, making it impossible to purchase pricey supplies. In addition, the materials needed to create the visual aids were expensive, so instead of spending money on other things, they decided to purchase the items they would need for their instruction.

Summary of Personal-Related Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers

Table 2.1e on the next page summarizes the respondents' responses to the personal challenges that the Practice-Teachers faced.

Table 2.1e
Summary of Personal-Related Challenges faced by Practice-Teachers

Indicators	WM	DE	Rank
1. Physical	2.88	S	1
2. Emotional	2.84	S	2
3. Social	2.51	S	4
4. Financial	2.82	S	3
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.76	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Table 2e shows the summary of the table of personal-related challenges faced by the respondents in terms of physical, emotional, social, and financial challenges, with an overall weighted mean of 2.76, which is described as "Sometimes". These indicators can sometimes be encountered by the Practice-Teachers in the period of their internship in the different schools they are deployed to. The biggest challenges that students encountered when taking their teaching internship in education were well-being and mental health, educational logistics, and restrictions (Fabro et al.,2023).

The highest is Indicator 1, with a weighted mean of 2.88, described as "Sometimes". This means that physical challenges are the most widely encountered challenge among the indicators. This implies that Practice-Teachers are more challenged in the physical aspect since the teaching profession demands many tasks that may lead to burnout, since the duties of a teacher do not end at school, and they need to deal with different challenges. Teaching is one of the most stressful professions (Saloviita & Pakarinen, 2021). According to the study by Collantes (2021), it states that Practice-Teachers face a variety of issues, such as cooperating teachers who fail to conduct routine class observations, talkative and noisy students, students who struggle to express themselves in English, an abundance of assignments from supervisors and school administrators, uncooperative student teachers, and a shortage of time and resources for creating lesson plans.

Indicator 3, got the lowest weighted mean with a total of 2.51, described as "Sometimes". This means that the social aspect is the least encountered challenge by the Practice-Teachers. Teaching is very open to socialization since this profession is a two-way process. Also, Practice-Teachers receive guidance, mentorship, and support from experienced educators and supervisors. This professional support can help Practice-

Teachers develop their social skills, handle interpersonal dynamics, and navigate challenging social situations with confidence. In an educational setting, teaching and learning can be viewed as social activities that entail relationships between the instructor and students, as well as between these parties (teacher-students) and materials, equipment, the classroom environment, and the curriculum. These relationships, which can be highly complex, are new to the students, who have previously only dealt with the teachers and the classroom's materials. As a result, students participating in teaching preparation must adjust well to the new setting (Sarıçoban, 2010). Because Practice-Teachers need to adapt to the ever-changing teaching and learning environment since the education process does not end just in one classroom setting.

A. Technological Knowledge

Table 2.2a presents the challenges faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of technological knowledge, which gained a weighted mean of 2.49, with a descriptive equivalent of "Rarely".

Indicator 8, "I experience difficulty in using/navigating advanced technologies provided by the DepEd", got the highest mean of 2.60, described as "Sometimes", which indicates that Practice-Teachers face several challenges when incorporating advanced technologies provided by DepEd into their teaching practices. Many Practice-Teachers may need to be more familiar with advanced technologies supplied by DepEd. They may need adequate training on effectively using advanced technologies in the classroom. According to Unite (2024), the President gave the Department of Education (DepEd) instructions to ensure that teachers have the appropriate training to use technology in the classroom more effectively. One of the things the agency needs to consider in raising the nation's PISA rating is the usage of technology by educators and pupils.

Table 2.2a
Academic Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Technological Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I experience difficulty in operating modernized technology due to lack of knowledge.	2.45	R	7
2. I experience challenge in using technology in delivering my lesson.	2.47	R	4
3. I experience struggle in balancing the usage of traditional and modernized technology for my instructional materials.	2.51	S	3
4. I experience hard time integrating appropriate technology in the teaching process.	2.44	R	9
5. I experience unfamiliarity on the applications used for better lesson presentation.	2.49	R	5
6. I experience difficulty in making modernized instructional materials because I don't have the necessary gadgets to be used.	2.41	R	10
7. I experience challenge in navigating lesson resources from social media platforms.	2.59	S	2
8. I experience difficulty in using/navigating advance technologies provided by the DepEd.	2.60	S	1
9. I experience difficulty in creating assessments using modern technologies.	2.45	R	8
10. I experience hard time in creating modern presentations that addresses different learning styles of students using technologies.	2.48	R	6
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.49	R	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest obtained mean was indicator 6, "I experience difficulty in making modernized instructional materials because I do not have the necessary gadgets to be used", with a mean of 2.41, described as "Rarely". This indicates that many Practice-Teachers have access to particular gadgets or tools that can significantly enhance their teaching experience. As a practice teacher, they can create a more interactive, engaging, and inclusive learning environment for the students. According to Roschelle (2003), there are various educational benefits of mobile technologies that are most often cited as quickly accessing content, integrating a broad range of academic activities, supporting independent study and student organization, encouraging student enthusiasm, supporting classroom-based collaboration and interaction as well as supporting inquiry-based instruction and learning.

A. Pedagogical Knowledge

Table 2.2b presents the challenges by Practice-Teachers in terms of Pedagogical Knowledge. Based on the ratings made by the respondents, the weighted mean is 2.84, with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes".

Table 2.2b
Academic Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of
Pedagogical Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I experience difficulty in implementing different teaching strategies that are responsive to the different learning styles of learners.	2.96	S	1
2. I experience difficulties in classroom management in the teaching and learning process.	2.87	S	5
3. I experience hard time in discussing my lesson using different languages and a range of strategies for communicating learner needs, progress and achievement.	2.95	S	2
4. I experience difficulty in applying theories I learned into the real field of teaching.	2.89	S	4
5. I experience struggle in formulating different assessment techniques that are adaptive to the diversity of learners.	2.92	S	3
6. I experience difficulty in relating the new lessons to the past ones.	2.65	S	10
7. I experience hard time in manipulating and using tools needed for the teaching process.	2.76	S	8.5
8. I experience struggle in formulating examples that is relevant to the real world scenarios.	2.76	S	8.5
9. I experience difficulty in constructing questions that addresses higher order skills.	2.85	S	6

10. I experience difficulty in maintaining interaction in the teaching and learning process.	2.77	S	7
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.84	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 1, "I experience difficulty in implementing different teaching strategies that are responsive to the different learning styles of learners", obtained the highest mean of 2.96 with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes". Implementing various teaching strategies to different learning styles can challenge Practice-Teachers. Some of these challenges may include limited training, seminars, and workshops to have exposure to diverse teaching strategies. Practice-Teachers must also put additional effort into organizing and preparing the lessons for a class since they may struggle to learn and comprehend the information, leading to a lack of focus on teaching strategies. According to (Stewart & Felicettie, 1992), learning is influenced by the educational conditions under which a student learns. Therefore, learning styles are more concerned about what students need to learn rather than how they want to learn effectively.

On the other hand, indicator 6, "I experience difficulty in relating the new lessons to the past ones", obtained the lowest mean of 2.65 with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes". This indicates that Practice-Teachers are experiencing less difficulty in relating their new lessons to the past ones. Practice-Teachers are also trained to align new lessons with previously taught materials, ensuring continuity and building upon existing knowledge. According to (Borg, 2003, and Crooks, 2015), the attempt to discover the impacts of previous experiences was based on the assumption that student teachers' practices have been shaped by their language learning histories, namely by their prior learning experiences and teacher cognition. It can be helpful for them to reflect on their learning journeys and consider how they made connections between past and present lessons.

B. Content Knowledge

Table 2.2c presents the challenges faced by Practice-Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge. Based on the data, the weighted mean is 2.73, with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes".

Table 2.2c
Academic Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers in
terms of Content Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I experience hard time in demonstrating content knowledge and its application within and/or across curriculum teaching areas.	2.80	S	1
2. I lack knowledge in the lessons I need to teach to my students.	2.54	S	10
3. I struggle implementing educational philosophies in the teaching and learning process.	2.72	S	6.5

4. I experience difficulty mastering theories applicable in classroom.	2.72	S	6.5
5. I struggle in making SMART objectives for my lessons.	2.76	S	4
6. I experience difficulty in making lesson plans aligned to the Curriculum.	2.78	S	3
7. I experience hard time in formulating comprehensive explanation regarding the content of subject matter.	2.79	S	2
8. I experience difficulty in understanding the curriculum.	2.69	S	8
9. I struggle in creating content relevant assessments.	2.66	S	9
10. I struggle in internalizing the concepts that I will teach to my students.	2.73	S	5
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.73	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 1, "I experience hard time in demonstrating content knowledge and its application within and across curriculum teaching areas", gained the highest mean of 2.80 with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes". This implies that Practice-Teachers may be new to teaching or have limited experience in the subject matter. Some subjects or concepts may be inherently more challenging to teach or require a deeper understanding, making it harder for Practice-Teachers to convey the material. According to Shulman (1986), teachers' knowledge of their subject matter and the importance of this knowledge for successful teaching. In addition, content knowledge about the teaching process, such as the best ways for students to acquire a subject's particular concepts and subjects and the most effective ways to express and communicate that content.

On the other hand, indicator 2, "I lack knowledge in the lessons I need to teach to my students", obtained the lowest mean of 2.54, with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes". This implies that the respondents have an understanding of the lessons that they need to teach to the students. With the experience and knowledge gained from higher Education, Practice-Teachers can meet the demands of the content of the topic to be presented to their students. Additionally, being knowledgeable about the subject matter enhances the credibility of Practice-Teachers and fosters trust and respect from the students. According to Ball (2010), the finest teaching strategies are those who are well-versed in the subject matter they teach and may employ to help the students grasp the material thoroughly. Thus, this will help Practice-Teachers understand and continue professional development in the subject matter.

Summary of Academic-Related Challenges Faced by Practice-Teachers

Table 2.2d summarizes the table of academic-related challenges faced by the respondents, with an overall weighted mean of 2.68 and a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes".

Table 2.2d
Summary of Academic-Related Challenges faced by Practice-Teachers

Indicators	WM	DE	Rank
1. Technological Knowledge	2.72	S	2
2. Pedagogical Knowledge	2.49	R	3
3. Content Knowledge	2.84	S	1
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.68	S	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 3 obtained the highest weighted mean of 2.84, described as "Sometimes". This suggests that Practice-Teachers experienced hardship in the knowledge of the subject matter since they were a product of online classes during the pandemic. Students who attend classes online often struggle academically for a variety of reasons. Higher levels of autonomy are needed from students in online learning than in in-person classes, which might be difficult for students with non-traditional enrollment trajectories or academic weaknesses (Dabbagh et al., 2019). Thus, the knowledge of the subject matter of Practice-Teachers was directly affected due to the transition from face-to-face to online during the pandemic.

Indicator 2, "Pedagogical Knowledge", obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.49, described as "Rarely". It implies that keeping up and staying updated with the latest teaching methodologies, strategies, and practices can be rarely challenging amidst evolving educational landscapes. Practice-Teachers typically undergo teacher training programs, which equip them with pedagogical knowledge and skills. The structured training helps Practice-Teachers build a foundation in pedagogy, making it less challenging for them during Practice. According to Filgona et al. (2020), pedagogy was the focus of most teaching research between the 1960s and 1980s, and it consists of general knowledge, beliefs, and skills related to teaching. It includes knowledge of the principle of instruction and knowledge and skills related to classroom management. To guarantee that Practice-Teachers can effectively mentor pre-service teachers and contribute to their professional growth, addressing these obstacles calls for continued professional development and assistance.

Coping Mechanisms Utilized by Practice-Teachers

This section presents the coping mechanisms used by the Practice-Teachers of Urdaneta City University regarding personal and academic issues.

A. Physical

Table 3.1a shows the Physical-Related Coping Mechanisms used by the respondents with a weighted mean of 3.75 and is described as "Often".

Indicator 4, "I louder my voice during the lesson to engage everybody in the class without too much moving around", obtained the highest mean of 4.16 with the descriptive equivalent "Often".

Table 3.1a
Personal Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Physical
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I confront the student making noise in the class calmly.	3.95	O	3
2. I take sometime to sit down during and after my discussions.	3.30	S	10
3. I usually use handy and lightweight materials for the teaching and learning process.	3.55	O	8
4. I louder my voice during the lesson to engage everybody in the class without too much moving around.	4.16	O	1
5. I talk with the students regarding the reason why they are doing such actions and behaviors.	3.90	O	5
6. I use fan and bring extra t-shirt that will ease the hotness of the surrounding.	3.22	S	9
7. I practice eye contact to my students without bending and kneeling to be in their eye level.	3.94	O	4
8. I create a schedule and practice time-management techniques.	3.81	O	6
9. I ask help from my students in organizing the room and I also implement classroom rules to maintain classroom cleanliness.	4.03	O	2
10. I utilize lightweight backpacks or bags with proper support.	3.72	O	7
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.76	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

This implies that most Practice-Teachers utilize the modulation of their voices to limit movement and deliver the lesson to all the students inside the classroom. Moreover, voice is the medium through which the teacher imparts knowledge to students; thus, making it audible will make the lesson more understandable. Denton (2007) states that language and voice are two of the most powerful tools for teachers. It fills every aspect of teaching and learning. In addition, we can only engage children in learning by using words. The messages that teachers impart to their students significantly affect how they behave, think, and eventually understand. Therefore, a louder voice is a way to make the lessons more audible for all students in the classroom, ensuring that all students can understand the topics or lessons being discussed.

The second highest mean is indicator 9, "I ask help from my students in organizing the room and I also implement classroom rules to maintain classroom cleanliness", with a mean of 4.03, described as "Often". This implies that a conducive and clean classroom is essential to maintaining a suitable environment for Education. A good environment makes everything go smoothly; that is why Practice-Teachers should be seen leading and employing rules that will support the organization of rooms. Similarly, as Manzano and Manzano (2003) studied, well-run classrooms offer an atmosphere conducive to teaching

and learning. However, a well-managed classroom does not just appear out of nowhere. It takes a good deal of effort to create, and the person who is most responsible for making it is the teacher.

On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest obtained mean was 2, "I take some time to sit down during and after my discussions", which was described as "Sometimes". This implies that it is the least coping method that the Practice-Teachers use since the teaching profession demands standing for long hours of teaching. Sitting down during a discussion on the part of Practice-Teachers is not a good action since they have training and application in the actual teaching world. According to the British Council, teachers must stand to get the entire class's attention, clarify language, or give directions because students can see them. Moreover, according to Indeed, as a practice teacher, it is not a good idea to sit down for an extended amount of time when there are students in the classroom. Some students may go off-topic or interfere with other learners' activities at the school, and walking around would prevent this. Thus, students can be encouraged to finish their work, and disruptive conduct can be reduced by watching them.

B. Emotional

As revealed in the table, the coping mechanisms used by Practice-Teachers in terms of emotion obtained a weighted mean of 3.80 with the descriptive equivalent of "Often".

Indicator 8, "I ask my cooperating teacher what should I do next to become better", obtained the highest mean of 4.01, described as "Often". It implies that Practice-Teachers frequently ask for help from their cooperating teachers since they are the ones who can provide the knowledge and guidance that they need for their improvement. Cooperating teachers are also the closest possible person whom they can count on. Anderson (2007) stated that student teachers frequently described their cooperating teachers as impacting their adjustments, and cooperating teachers were shown to exert power over their student teachers through assessments, rewards, and knowledge dissemination. Hence, cooperating teachers play a vital role in enhancing the skills, knowledge, and capabilities of Practice-Teachers that they can use in the actual teaching world.

Table 3.1b
Personal Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Emotional
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I asked advice regarding my challenges from my cooperating teacher.	3.93	O	5
2. I prioritize tasks, create a realistic schedule, and learn to say no to additional commitments.	3.58	O	8
3. I lower my expectations and just do my tasks one at a time.	3.49	S	9
4. I control my emotions after I get angry in front of my students.	3.76	S	7
5. I seek guidance from my cooperating teacher on handling challenging interactions.	3.96	O	4
6. I ask questions on my students about my lessons.	3.98	O	3
7. I just keep moving forward and I lower my expectations.	3.48	S	10
8. I ask my cooperating teacher what should I do next to become more better.	4.01	O	1
9. I seek support from my friends and other family members.	3.84	O	6

10. I cultivate empathy for my students, communicate and seek advice from my cooperating teacher.	4.00	O	2
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.80	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 7, "I just keep moving forward, and I lower my expectations", obtained the lowest mean of 3.48, categorized as "Sometimes". This signifies that Practice-Teachers do not lower their expectations; instead, they take it more seriously and use it to motivate themselves to improve their work later on. Setting high standards for learners helps produce exciting and engaging work that boosts confidence, helps them develop a sense of self, and helps them do better academically (Brophy, 2008; 2010). Confidence among students is crucial because it correlates with their readiness to take on challenging learning tasks.

C. Social

Table 3.1c details the coping strategies along with social. It presents the weighted mean of 3.97 and is described as "Often".

Indicator 4, "I build good relationships with my students and show my genuine interest in their lives", gained the highest mean of 4.13 with the descriptive equivalent of "Often". This means that building a good relationship with their students is essential for creating a positive and productive learning environment; showing genuine interest in their lives lets them know they are crucial, such as asking about their opinions, interests, and background. When Practice-Teachers intentionally try to get to know their students, it can foster a sense of belonging in students and build an excellent connection to the school, building a foundation for academic success. According to the study of Downey (2008), the relationship quality between a student and a teacher will result in a greater degree of learning in the classroom. This suggests that when students feel supported, they are more likely to engage in learning and have a better academic outcome. The better the relationship between Practice-Teachers and students, the more it will lead to increased cooperation in the classroom, which will also contribute to the social learning of every learner.

Table 3.1c
Personal Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Social
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I make an effort to meet new people. I recognize and deal with negative thoughts and beliefs that may be contributing to my feeling of being out of place.	3.96	O	7
2. I remain calm, I take deep breath and give my students an opportunity to express themselves and be heard.	4.12	O	2.5
3. I focus on my strengths and I acknowledge my unique qualities and talents.	4.06	O	5

4.	I build good relationship with my students and show my genuine interest on their lives.	4.13	O	1
5.	I use clear and concise language to ensure a good communication with my students.	4.12	O	2.5
6.	I address any behavior issues promptly and directly in a calm and controlled manner.	4.09	O	4
7.	I use multiple communication channels, such as emails and phone calls to reach out with the parents and families of my students.	3.59	O	10
8.	I showed empathy and understanding to my students by acknowledging their feelings and perspectives.	4.01	O	6
9.	I reached out to experienced teachers or mentors who have worked with similar grade levels or age groups.	3.89	O	8
10.	I communicated often with the different stakeholder of the school.	3.72	O	9
WEIGHTED MEAN		3.97	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

On the other hand, indicator 7, "I use multiple communication channels, such as emails and phone calls to reach out with the parents and families of my students", receives the lowest mean of 3.59 with the descriptive equivalent of "Often". It signifies that the task of Practice-Teachers seldom includes communicating with the parents of their students but more to teaching and assisting their cooperating teachers among non-academic tasks. Based on the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers Article IX, Section 1, "Every teacher shall establish and maintain cordial relations with parents, and shall conduct himself to merit their confidence and respect". For that reason, teachers are obliged to communicate with the students' parents as classroom facilitators.

D. Financial

Table 3.1d presents the weighted mean of 3.65 and is described as "Often", which means that there are existing strategies to cope with financial difficulty among the Practice-Teachers, as mentioned below.

Table 3.1d
Personal Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Financial
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I create a monthly budget for taking control of my finances to avoid spending too much.	3.39	S	9
2. I always choose to ride on the cheapest public transportation.	3.89	O	1
3. I reach out to my family and to my fellow pre-service teacher for coping with financial stress.	3.31	S	10
4. I take control of managing my own money and I impose discipline on myself regarding spending.	3.70	O	6
5. I make adjustments in my budget and lifestyle if needed.	3.79	O	2

6. I save my own money to help me build a stable financial in the future.	3.73	O	4.5
7. I take time in learning financial literacy knowledge and try to practice it.	3.65	O	7
8. I plan regarding the things I am buying to prevent allowance insufficiency.	3.73	O	4.5
9. I use recyclable or cheap materials for my lessons if possible.	3.61	O	8
10. I analyze my expenses to see which ones I can reduce or remove.	3.75	O	3
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.65	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 2, "I always choose to ride on the cheapest public transportation", gained the highest mean of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of "Often". Practiced teachers must travel from home to school, and the most typical and widely used transportation for Practice-Teachers has always been the cheapest public transportation. It is already an accustomed practice or a necessity for student transportation. Public transport can also be beneficial in many ways, such as promoting student productivity.

According to Wilkie (2010), this transportation mode plays a significant role in encouraging profitability and opportunity by moving aptitudes, work, and learning. Since Practice-Teachers need to balance how they spend their finances, choosing the cheapest public transportation can be beneficial for them, and they can also manage their time since riding public transit can be more convenient than selecting a private vehicle, significantly saving them from saving their money.

On the other hand, Indicator 3, "I reach out to my family and my fellow pre-service teacher for coping with financial stress", gained the lowest mean of 3.31. Indicator 3 shows that reaching out about money is challenging for their fellow practice teacher. Practice-Teachers do not want others to know how much or how little they have, and feeling judged was the top reason people cited holding them back from talking about their money. Reaching out to their family may be challenging because they want to avoid adding some burden. This may be due to a study conducted by Durisic and Bunijevac (2017), which states that reaching out to family can be difficult because parents are often preoccupied with the distractions and demands of daily life. Burdened by low income, inflexible work hours, and language barriers, some parents cannot attend school activities or regularly participate in their children's schooling. Lastly, Practice-Teachers may struggle and need help beginning a conversation about money because it brings up thousands of insecurities and doubts. They seem scared to look money in the face and to put themselves out there, formally stating where they stand in a value equation.

Summary of Personal-Related Coping Mechanisms Utilized by Practice-Teachers

Table 3.1e shows the summary of the table of Academic-Related Coping Mechanisms utilized by the respondents with an overall weighted mean of 3.80 with a descriptive equivalent of "Sometimes".

Among these aspects, Indicator 3, which focuses on the Social aspect, obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.97 and is described as "Often". This indicates that the respondents actively employ coping mechanisms to address these social challenges. They may utilize techniques such as building positive relationships, establishing effective communication channels, fostering a supportive classroom environment, and managing conflicts or challenging interactions. A primary distinguishing characteristic of the teachers is their tendency to seek support from teachers, mentors, and administrators as they conquer exhausting and discouraging challenges. They also overcome challenges by seeking family support. The support group system allowed the teachers to share personal experiences and feelings through a core network of people close to their lives. Seeking core support and inspiration from the teacher's support group provided insights and approaches to a problem, according to Baraquia (2022). Furthermore, coping strategies utilized by the Practice-Teachers in the social aspect would provide a more comprehensive understanding of their experiences and shed light on the effectiveness of these coping mechanisms in managing social challenges during their internship.

Table 3.1e
Summary of Personal-Related Coping Utilized by Practice-Teachers

Indicators	WM	DE	Rank
1. Physical	3.76	O	3
2. Emotional	3.80	O	2
3. Social	3.97	O	1
4. Financial	3.65	O	4
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.80	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

The Financial aspect obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.65, with a descriptive equivalent of "Often". It suggests that Practice-Teachers minimally turn to financial strategies as a coping mechanism during their teaching internship. The possible reason why the utilization of financial strategies is least utilized could be attributed to various reasons beyond the availability of financial assistance from the government, scholarships, or enhanced financial literacy among Practice-Teachers. To be fully equipped with knowledge and understanding of the basic concept of financial literacy is essential; it gives individuals an advantage in carefully and properly managing their financial budget,

according to Casingal (2022). This statement indicates that Practice-Teachers do not depend on financial strategies as coping mechanisms during their teaching internships since they are already aware and possess financial literacy that makes them deal with problems readily and easily. At the same time, they are manageable in terms of finances since the government provides various opportunities and support for students like them.

A. Technological Knowledge

As shown in Table 3.2a, Coping Mechanisms along with the Technological Knowledge.

Table 3.2a
Academic Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Technological Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I follow the step by step procedure of how to use modernized technology.	4.06	O	1
2. I seek guidance from my mentors about the proper way to use technology in delivering lessons.	4.02	O	2
3. I plan regarding what appropriate instructional materials will I use beforehand.	3.98	O	4
4. I consult guidance on experienced teachers who can provide valuable insights and guidance on integrating technology into the classroom.	3.93	O	6
5. I watch instructional videos about creating innovative presentations of lessons.	4.00	O	3
6. I borrow gadgets from my friends, classmates or relatives.	3.22	S	10
7. I evaluate online resources thoroughly.	3.66	O	9
8. I take time in learning the manuals in how to use technologies provided by the DepEd.	3.82	O	8
9. I read different resources regarding the procedure on creating assessments.	3.90	O	7
10. I create presentations which appeals to the different senses.	3.95	O	5
WEIGHTED MEAN	3.85	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 1, "I follow the step-by-step procedure of how to use modernized technology", gained the highest mean of 4.06 with the descriptive equivalent of "Often". Practice-Teachers rely heavily on following step-by-step procedures when using modernized technology as a coping strategy to address technological challenges. This approach provides them with a clear and structured framework for navigating the complexities of technology. Because of the abundance of available educational technology, teachers feel comfortable and confident about using it effectively (Johnson et al., 2016). By adhering to a defined procedure, Practice-Teachers can build confidence, troubleshoot issues effectively, ensure consistency in their use of technology, optimize resource utilization, and engage in ongoing professional development. A step-by-step

procedure enables Practice-Teachers to overcome technological challenges and utilize modernized technology to enhance their teaching practices.

On the other hand, indicator 6, "I borrow gadgets from my friends, classmates or relatives", got the lowest mean of 3.22 and is described as "Sometimes". This indicates that most Practice-Teachers have their gadgets for teaching in modern society. Technological progress such as laptops, smartphones, tablets, computers, and other technologies have become one of the most used, leading to innovation in the world of Education. Gadgets are a proliferating technological tool with special functions, including smartphones and tablets (Fauzi, 2018). Practice-Teachers often seek long-term solutions rather than relying on borrowing gadgets as a temporary coping mechanism. They may prefer to acquire their own devices or explore institutional support to ensure consistent and reliable access to technology, reducing the need to depend on others.

B. Pedagogical Knowledge

Table 3.2b presents the weighted mean of 4.10, described as "Often". It shows the coping mechanisms of the respondents with pedagogical knowledge.

Table 3.2b
Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Pedagogical Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I plan my instruction and I am grouping students flexibly to help them address their individual strengths and needs.	4.12	O	6
2. I implement class rules in the classroom.	4.20	O	2
3. I practice using appropriate languages for my lesson.	4.24	O	1
4. I seek guidance from mentors and I continuously practice to master the art of teaching.	4.11	O	5
5. I attend seminars and workshops that help me in different assessment techniques for my students.	3.94	O	9
6. I make sure that there is a review of the previous lesson to be able to connect the new lesson.	4.10	O	7
7. I practice in using needed tools in the teaching process.	4.09	O	8
8. I plan regarding the examples I will share to my students.	4.15	O	4
9. I seek guidance from my former teachers.	3.90	O	10
10. I use activities that are engaging to maintain interaction in the class.	4.19	O	3
WEIGHTED MEAN	4.10	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 3, "I practice using appropriate languages for my lesson", gained the highest mean of 4.24, described as "Often". This implies that most Practice-Teachers consistently use appropriate or prescribed languages to improve learning. Also, Practice-Teachers align their language use with educational standards and curriculum requirements.

According to Glatthorn (1990), representation of the ideas in the form of new analogies and metaphors of teachers' knowledge, including how they speak about teaching, not only includes references to what teachers should do but also includes presenting the material using figurative language and metaphors. Furthermore, to teach all students according to today's standards, teachers must understand the subject matter deeply and flexibly to help students create useful cognitive maps, relate one idea to another, and address misconceptions. Teachers need to see how ideas connect across fields and to everyday life. This kind of understanding provides a foundation for pedagogical content knowledge that enables teachers to make ideas accessible to others, (Shulman, 1987). This statement emphasizes the importance of teachers having a deep and flexible understanding of their subject matter. With this deep understanding, Practice-Teachers can help students develop a clear understanding of concepts, connect ideas across different topics, and address any misconceptions. This understanding also forms the basis for pedagogical content knowledge, enabling teachers to communicate and make complex ideas accessible to their students effectively.

On the other hand, Indicator 9, "I seek guidance from my former teachers", gained the lowest mean of 3.90 and was described as "Often". This suggests that while teachers sometimes seek guidance from their former teachers, it is not standard practice during their internship but somehow compelling and can make a change. Their former teachers may have limited availability or commitments that make it challenging to provide ongoing guidance. Practice-Teachers may also prefer to explore diverse perspectives and approaches to teaching, drawing from a range of resources such as professional networks, mentorship programs, or online communities. According to DepEd Order No. 42 (2017), teachers prioritize personal and professional reflection and continuous learning to enhance their practice. They take responsibility for their growth and development, actively seeking opportunities to improve their professional knowledge and skills. By reflecting on their own needs and considering the needs of their colleagues and students, teachers strive to continually enhance their teaching practice and provide the best possible Education. This highlights the importance of personal and professional reflection for Practice-Teachers to improve their practice. It emphasizes their responsibility for lifelong learning and continuous development, encouraging them to actively seek opportunities to enhance their professional knowledge and skills by considering their needs and those of their colleagues and students.

C. Content Knowledge

The weighted mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of "Often", shows that the respondents cope with the challenges encountered along with content knowledge.

Indicator 7, "I watch instructional videos that can impart supplementary knowledge", has the highest mean of 4.13 and a descriptive equivalent of "Often". Most Practice-Teachers frequently watch instructional videos to gain supplementary knowledge. Also, it indicates that the respondents recognize the value and importance of using instructional videos to enhance their teaching practices and expand their knowledge base.

Table 3.2c
Coping Mechanisms of Practice-Teachers in terms of Content Knowledge
N=282

Indicators	M	DE	Rank
1. I revisit and relearn the contents of the curriculum and practice to teach it thoroughly.	4.03	O	5
2. I practice self-study, dedicate extra time to thoroughly understand the lesson material. I utilize textbooks, online resources, or educational videos to enhance my knowledge.	4.06	O	4
3. I seek mentorship or guidance from experienced educators who have successfully integrated these philosophies.	4.01	O	6.5
4. I relearn the theories that I can use in the teaching and learning process.	3.82	O	10
5. I stick with the SMART characteristics of lesson objectives.	3.95	O	8
6. I make my lesson plan thoroughly and make sure that it is align to the curriculum.	4.10	O	2
7. I watch instructional videos which can impart supplementary knowledge.	4.13	O	1
8. I seek help from my colleagues.	3.91	O	9
9. I read informative resources regarding formulating assessments.	4.01	O	6.5
10. I read extensively regarding my topics.	4.09	O	3
WEIGHTED MEAN	4.01	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

According to Ljubojevic et al. (2014), segmenting teaching materials with supplementary video clips can enhance the organization and presentation of lectures, leading to more effective teaching and learning. Additionally, Brame C. J. (2016) highlights the significance of educational videos in Higher Education, particularly in flipped, blended, and online classes, as they serve as valuable tools for delivering content to students. This statement suggests incorporating segmented teaching materials with supplementary video clips can benefit their instructional approach. By organizing and presenting lectures segmented, Practice-Teachers can enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning experiences. Furthermore, educational videos can be valuable tools for delivering content and engaging students in higher education settings, especially in flipped, blended, and online classes. Practice-Teachers can consider leveraging these strategies to optimize teaching methods and promote effective learning outcomes.

On the other hand, indicator 4, "I relearn the theories that I can use in the teaching and learning process", received the lowest mean of 3.82 and was described as "Often". This means that while the respondents often revisit and relearn theories relevant to the teaching and learning process, this practice needs to be more consistently observed. It suggests that the respondents engage in this practice regularly but not as frequently or as thoroughly as the other practices for some reason. One reason is familiarity and confidence with the theories can influence their utilization. Practice-Teachers who feel confident in their existing knowledge and teaching methods may not see the need to

revisit or relearn theories. They may rely on their expertise and past experiences to address content challenges.

Sandt (2018) highlights cross-cultural differences regarding beliefs and practices, the quality of the learning environment, the strength of teachers' beliefs in their efficacy (self-efficacy), and their job satisfaction. This means past experiences and successes influence self-efficacy. When teachers have previously achieved positive outcomes in their teaching practices, they develop a belief in their ability to navigate challenges and achieve desired results effectively. These successful experiences contribute to their confidence in their efficacy.

Summary of Academic-Related Coping Mechanisms Utilized by Practice-Teachers

Table 3.2d shows the summary of the respondent's responses on the personal related coping strategies that they utilized to deal with the challenges in terms of Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge, and Content Knowledge with an overall weighted mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of "Often".

Table 3.2d
Summary of Academic-Related Coping Mechanisms Utilized by Practice-Teachers

Indicators	WM	DE	Rank
1. Technological Knowledge	3.85	O	3
2. Pedagogical Knowledge	4.10	O	1
3. Content Knowledge	4.01	O	2
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.99	O	

Legend:

Mean Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50-5.00	Always (A)
3.50-4.49	Often (O)
2.50-3.49	Sometimes (S)
1.50-2.49	Rarely (R)
1.00-1.49	Never (N)

Indicator 2, Pedagogical Knowledge, obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.10, categorized as "Often". This implies that pedagogical knowledge fosters problem-solving skills in Practice-Teachers. Further, when encountering obstacles or difficulties in teaching, such as low student engagement or learning gaps, teachers can apply their pedagogical expertise to identify solutions and implement interventions to address these challenges. Despite having the content knowledge, it will not be effective without the art of teaching or the way the teacher teaches and delivers every lesson in the class. Thus, the emphasis on coping with the new trends of teaching strategies and approaches must be properly possessed. According to Haron et al. (2020), pedagogical content knowledge represents the blending of content and pedagogy into an understanding of how particular topics, problems, or issues are organized, represented, and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners and presented for instruction. Thus, without pedagogy, content knowledge will not be effective since it will not be delivered well to the learners.

Indicator 1, Technological Knowledge, got the lowest weighted mean of 3.85 with a descriptive equivalent of "Often". This implies that Practice-Teachers in modern society minimally need technological knowledge as a coping since most of them are digital natives. Due to that, they are already aware and knowledgeable about the usage of different technologies. Thus, continuous training to learn the ways and proper application of technology is needed. At the same time, the technology usage has been part of the curriculum that the Practice-Teachers already take. According to CHED Memorandum No. 74, s. 2017, Students should be able to apply skills in the development and utilization of ICT to promote quality, relevant, and sustainable educational practice. That is why part of the required subjects to be taken is Technology for Teaching and Learning 1 and 2 in all programs of the College of Teacher Education. With that, Practice-Teachers are already well-known about technology since it is rampant now. At the same time, some subjects focus on imparting information and skills about ICT and technologies.

Overall, the TPACK Theory Framework, specifically Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge, is needed for Practice-Teachers as it encompasses the crucial things that a practice teacher must embody in the 21st century.

Significant Difference on the Challenges Faced by the Practice-Teachers across their Profile Variables

Tables 4a and 4b show the significant difference between the challenges faced by Practice-Teachers across their profile variables.

It can be seen in the table on the next page that there is a significant difference between the specialization of the respondents and the physical challenges faced by Practice-Teachers, with a significance of .032.

Table 4a
Significant Difference on the Personal-Related Challenges Faced by the Respondents across their Profile Variables

	Physical		Emotional		Social		Financial	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Age	1.729	.102	2.007	.054	.517	.822	1.530	.157
Sex	.537	.464	.082	.775	.493	.483	.001	.977
Specialization	2.015	.032	2.693	.004	2.796	.003	1.042	.408
Gadgets used in teaching	.892	.469	.381	.822	1.145	.336	1.059	.377

This implies that different specializations or majors experienced different physical challenges. This can be because the focus of different specializations varies. Different subjects require different physical activities, and some teaching methods are more physically demanding than others. According to the study of Napanoy et.al (2021),

problems encountered by pre-service teachers vary from each field of specialization. This includes physical challenges such as the involvement of pre-service teachers in activities in and out of the school, skills needed to perform the task, inadequate instructional materials, crowded classrooms, inadequate laboratory equipment, and other facilities.

Furthermore, there is a significant difference between the specialization of the respondents and the emotional challenges encountered by the Practice-Teachers, with a significance of .004. This indicates a substantial gap between the respondents' emotional difficulties and their area of specialization. Practice-Teachers specializing in different subjects may face distinct emotional challenges based on the nature of the content they teach. For example, a practice teacher specializing in a complex topic like Mathematics may experience stress about conveying abstract concepts. In contrast, a teacher specializing in Arts may face emotional challenges linked to fostering creativity and expression. The investigation found that the specialization failed to meet the curriculum's required goals. It was just evolving into teaching rather than training. The main issues and challenges for its effective implementation and output were explored, including the lack of motivation and dedication of aspiring teachers, the commitment and integrity of supervisors, the cooperation of cooperating schools, university policies, job opportunities in the home country, and unfair and flexible evaluation practices (Adhikari, 2022).

Lastly, there is a significant difference in the specialization of the respondents to the social challenges faced by Practice-Teachers, with a significance of .003. This suggests that the respondents' areas of specialization and their social issues differ significantly. Specialization can lead to significant differences in social dynamics because people with different majors often have unique knowledge, skills, and perspectives. This can affect how they interact, communicate, and relate to each other within social settings. The diversity of majors and specializations in Education reflects the multifaceted nature of society, leading to varying social problems depending on the focus and context of each discipline. Abas (2016) states that there are varied perceptions of the difficulties of pre-service teachers from different significant programs. He identified that problems generally relate to students, assigned tasks, and learning environments.

Table 4b
Significant Difference on the Academic-Related Challenges Faced by the Respondents across their Profile Variables

	Technological Knowledge		Pedagogical Knowledge		Content Knowledge	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Age	.838	.556	1.191	.308	1.392	.208
Sex	.471	.493	.460	.498	1.088	.298
Specialization	1.081	.377	2.298	.013	1.786	.063
Gadgets used in teaching	1.491	.205	.431	.786	.558	.693

It can be seen in the table above that there is a significant difference between the specialization of the respondents and the Pedagogical Knowledge challenges faced by Practice-Teachers, with a significance of .013. This implies that while Practice-Teachers may face both challenges, they are distinct and require different approaches for effective resolution. The specific pedagogical challenges faced in various teacher education majors are influenced by the nature of the subject, the skills required, the diversity of student needs, and the demands of effective curriculum design, assessment, and classroom management. Thus, Practice-Teachers need to develop competence in their specialized subject area while honing their pedagogical skills to address the broader challenges of teaching and learning. Similarly, the duration of teaching experience and the specialization of teachers do not have a connection with their use of motivational techniques. It has significant outcomes for the teacher preparation department, as they must consider the motivational strategy approach they employ while designing their curricula (Zulkifli & Kutty, 2022).

Post Hoc Result on the Significant Difference of the Challenges Faced by the Practice-Teachers across their Profile Variables

Table 4c

Challenges	Specialization	Mean	Mean Diff.	t-value	Sig.
Physical	BSEPEHM	2.40	-.443	.843	.003
	BSEENG	2.84			
Emotional	BSNEd	2.60	-.133	.852	.041
	BSEPEHM	2.73			
Social	BSEPEHM	2.10	-.188	.698	.049
	BSEENG	2.28			
Pedagogical Knowledge ed	BSNEd	3.80	.913	.914	.031
	BSEPEHM	2.88			

The result shows that there is a significant difference in terms of physical challenges and the area of specialization of the Practice-Teachers. BSE PEHM and BSEd English are the specializations that had a difference in the physical challenges that they faced in their practice teaching. The table shows that BSEd English got a higher mean than BSEPEHM. This implies that English majors mainly experienced physical struggles since they needed to exert effort in checking the activities they were giving to their students, such as grammar and vocabulary. In fact, according to Muzamil and Javid (2023), in order to enhance writing skills, frequent writing assignments and feedback sessions are provided with a focus on grammar, vocabulary, and overall coherence. Thus, adding to the Practice-Teachers' workload leads to physical fatigue.

Moreover, there is a significant difference in the Practice-Teachers' areas of specialization and emotional challenges. A Bachelor of Special Needs Education and a Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Physical Education, Health, and Music made a difference. Of the 2, a Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Physical Education had the highest mean, suggesting that majors in physical education, health, and music practice experience physical challenges more frequently. This indicates that teaching physically demanding subjects requires active participation, movement, and energy expenditure, which can lead to physical exhaustion. This physical fatigue can contribute to emotional exhaustion and heightened stress levels among PE teachers. According to Gaudreault et al. (2018), PE teachers could internalize unpleasant emotions concerning marginalization, which could compromise their teaching, and it seems that marginalized teachers may be more likely to experience burnout, which is marked by physical and emotional exhaustion, relative to one's teaching.

Additionally, there is a significant difference in terms of social challenges and the area of specialization of Practice-Teachers. This means that there is a difference between a Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Physical Education, Health, and Music and a Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English. Thus, the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English got the highest mean, which implies that English major Practice-Teachers mostly encounter social challenges. This implies that developing relationships and fostering social interaction with students was difficult for English majors' Practice-Teachers. It can be attributed to the fact that they are expected to be fluent in the English language, resulting in pressure and fear to interact within and outside the classroom. As stated in the study of Jaya et.al (2022), pre-service teachers majoring in English have an intense need to speak English clearly and fluently. However, comprehension in language classes and social interaction outside the classroom are socially related issues.

Furthermore, there is a significant difference in pedagogical knowledge and the section on specialization of Practice-Teachers. Bachelor of Special Needs Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education, majoring in Physical Education, Health, and Music, had a difference. This shows that Bachelor of Special Needs Education got the highest mean of 3.80, indicating that the BSNEd Practice-Teachers thoroughly encounter challenges in terms of Pedagogical Knowledge. This can be challenging for them, mainly because they are new to the real-world classroom set-up and the program is still in its explorative stage. Hence, it might be challenging to implement all the pedagogical approaches and strategies required in the field. Moreover, effective learning is said to depend heavily on the strategies of the Practice-Teachers and the learner's motivation. Nonetheless, additional elements like intellect, prior knowledge, and interest all play a significant function as well. Thus, according to Rheinberg (2010), strategies should be considered in the context of teaching SPED classes. Motivation and applicable strategies in teaching are an activating orientation to a target status, which is regarded as positive in teaching-learning situations.

Significant Difference on the Coping Strategies Utilized by the Practice-Teachers across their Profile Variables

Tables 5a and 5b show the significant difference in the coping mechanisms utilized by Practice-Teachers across their profile variables.

The table shows that there is a significant difference between age and personal-related coping mechanisms in terms of physical, with a p-value of 2.044 and a significance of .050. This means that age can cause variations in how teachers cope with the physical demands of their profession; individual differences, experiences, and support systems also play significant roles. It is essential to recognize the diverse needs of teachers across different age groups and provide resources and support to promote their physical well-being in the classroom. Additionally, other physical coping mechanisms happen to varying ages because young people, grown-ups, and older people have different bodies and experiences. A steady decline in several aspects of bodily ability, such as aerobic power and capacity, muscular strength and endurance, and heat stress tolerance, is linked to aging (Shephard, 1999). Moreover, Van Kim and Nelson (2013) found that students who engaged in frequent vigorous physical activity were less likely to report poor mental health and perceived stress than students who exercised less frequently.

Table 5a

Significant Difference on the Personal-Related Coping Mechanisms Utilized by the Respondents across their Profile Variables

	Physical		Emotional		Social		Financial	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Age	2.044	.050	2.560	.014	1.894	.071	1.623	.129
Sex	1.260	.263	4.562	.034	3.427	.065	2.461	.118
Specialization	.774	.654	1.113	.353	2.483	.007	1.379	.190
Gadgets used	1.318	.263	.589	.671	1.625	.168	.717	.581

Second, there is a significant difference between the age of the respondents and their coping mechanisms in terms of emotions, with a p-value of 2.560 and a significance of .014. This implies that age influences how Practice-Teachers handle emotional challenges. Older Practice-Teachers may exhibit more effective coping mechanisms due to their accumulated life experience, refined emotional regulation skills, and adaptive strategies. With their life experience acquired, older people may be able to deliberately avoid circumstances that could cause them to feel emotionally distressed (Blanchard-Fields, 2007). This significant difference underscores the impact of age on coping mechanisms, highlighting the importance of considering teachers' age in understanding their responses to emotional challenges in the teaching profession. Research shows that teachers' well-being is related to many aspects, such as workload or students' classroom

behavior (Chan et al., 2021), emotion regulation, a positive work environment, and teachers' self-efficacy (feeling successful as a teacher) (Collie et al., 2015; Sohail et al., 2023); and contextual factors such as institutional resources and the amount of support received (Kumpikaitė- Valiūnienė et al., 2021). They understand the teaching interns' emotional health by highlighting the link between well-being and stress management strategies. This study highlights several coping mechanisms that teachers use when faced with challenges.

Additionally, there is a significant difference between specialization and personal-related coping mechanisms in terms of social, with a p-value of 2.483 and a significance of .007. This means that different specializations or subject areas yield differences in the social coping strategies employed during their internship. Recognizing and addressing teachers' unique social dynamics and support needs in other subject areas is essential for fostering a supportive and collaborative work environment. Through the specialization of Practice-Teachers, they may cope with challenges by diving deeper into their subject matter. Also, they may find relief and satisfaction in their major, improving their challenges management. Coping mechanisms for social challenges involve interpersonal relationships and social support systems. Practice-Teachers may seek support from colleagues, friends, or family members. Also, they can participate in group activities or discussions with other Practice-Teachers in which they are on the same program to share experiences and advice. According to Wang et al. (2022), Practice-Teachers regularly adopt an adaptive set of social coping strategies when dealing with stressful situations in class. Different majors in teacher education experience other problems, leading to variations in coping mechanisms.

Lastly, there is a significant difference between the sex and their coping mechanisms in terms of emotions, with a p-value of 4.562 and a significance of .034. It signifies that societal expectations and gender norms play a significant role in shaping emotional coping strategies. From younger individuals, boys and girls often socialize differently in expressing and managing emotions. Boys are commonly encouraged to suppress emotions, while girls may be encouraged to express them. The study by Whittle et al. (2011) revealed significant sex differences in the neural mechanisms underlying emotional processes. The researchers found that males and females tend to employ distinct strategies during emotional processing, which may contribute to the observed or subjectively reported sex differences in emotional experiences. It also suggests marked biological differences in the structure and function of brain regions involved in emotion, such as the amygdala and prefrontal cortex, between men and women. These neurobiological sex differences likely play a crucial role in influencing how individuals of different sexes process and regulate their emotions.

Table 5b
Significant Difference on the Academic-Related Coping Mechanisms Utilized by the Respondents across their Profile Variables

	Technological Knowledge		Pedagogical Knowledge		Content Knowledge	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Age	1.600	.135	2.58	.014	2.819	.008
Sex	.375	.541	1.509	.220	2.074	.151

Specialization	1.286	.238	1.296	.238	1.712	.078
Gadgets used in teaching	.874	.480	1.101	.356	1.081	.366

It can be seen in Table 5b that there is a significant difference between age and pedagogical knowledge, with a p-value of 2.58 and a significance of 0.14. This suggests that the pedagogical coping of Practice-Teachers varies in different ages. Practice-Teachers of different ages may have different pedagogical knowledge and approaches depending on their acquired knowledge and skills. Teachers with more years of experience, according to Zakar and Aslihan (2012), have different attitudes, better interactions with students, class control, and decision-making skills. In high school, older teachers are better at classroom management and more successful than younger teachers. This means that to meet the changing and increasing learning demands, Practice-Teachers are continually challenged to provide appropriate and timely professional development measures that will enhance Practice-Teachers' skills, knowledge, and attitudes.

Moreover, there is a significant difference between the age of the respondents and their coping mechanisms in terms of content knowledge, with a p-value of 2.819 and a significance of .008. This implies that more aged Practice-Teachers with more experience are better equipped to develop coping strategies that effectively address content-related challenges. Their accumulated wisdom, extensive personal experiences, and ability to adapt instructional approaches are crucial in navigating complex content issues in teaching. Furthermore, age brings a deeper understanding of curriculum development, assessment practices, and content standards, enhancing the Practice-Teachers' capacity to cope with the demands of content knowledge challenges. This significant difference underscores the profound disconnection between age and the coping strategies teachers employ to manage and overcome obstacles related to content knowledge in their teaching roles. The study by Ismail et.al (2018) concludes that there is a difference in the content effectiveness of teachers based on their age, suggesting that older teachers are more productive than younger ones. They are ready to raise the standard of instruction and learning and are concerned about adopting the new (HOT skills).

In sum, there are aspects of coping mechanisms with significant differences among the profile variables. In line with that, Richard Lazarus' Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping states that different people may view or perceive the same challenges differently, leading to differences in their coping strategies. Thus, different Practice-Teachers with different profiles use various coping strategies for their challenges.

Post Hoc Result on the Significant Difference of the Coping Mechanisms by the Practice-Teachers across their Profile Variables

Table 5c

Coping	Age	Mean	Mean Diff.	t-value	Sig.
Physical	2 (22)	3.72	.518	.734	.049
	7 (29)	3.20			

Emotional	2 (22) 7 (29)	3.77 2.80	.968	1.209	.016
Pedagogical	2 (22) 7 (29)	4.06 3.60	.458	.580	.021
Content Knowledge	2 (22) 7 (29)	3.96 3.30	.665	.832	.017
Coping					
	Profile	Mean	Mean Diff.	t-value	Sig.
Emotional	Sex Male Female	3.64 3.87	-.229	-2.136	.034
Social	Specialization 6 (BSEPEHM) 10 (BSEENG)	4.60 4.19	.413	.478	.036

In terms of coping mechanisms, a significant difference is observed in age and the physical coping strategies utilized by the respondents. Twenty-two year-old got a mean of 3.72, while 29-year-olds obtained a mean of 3.20, which indicates that they had a difference. Therefore, at 22 years of age, teachers use the most coping mechanisms in terms of physical aspects. This signifies that 22 years of age Practice-Teachers are utilizing coping mechanisms more extensively; this can be due to the fact that they are more open to diverse strategies when dealing with challenges in the physical aspect, and since they are younger, their bodies can do many things that need to exert energy.

According to Norheim et al. (2017), An aging body is linked to a progressive loss of strength, power, and muscular mass and a decrease in lung capacity, postural control, and maximal oxygen consumption (VO₂max).

Additionally, there is a significant difference in terms of the age of the Practice-Teachers and their emotional coping mechanisms. The difference can be observed between 22 and 29 years old, with 3.77 and 2.80, respectively. As a result, The higher mean for the 22-year-old Practice-Teachers indicates that individuals in this age group rely more on emotional coping mechanisms to deal with challenges in their teaching roles. Therefore, Practice-Teachers at the age of 22 may lean towards emotional coping strategies as a primary means of managing and navigating through the emotional challenges they encounter. A study by Smith and Johnson (2018) found that younger teachers often face higher levels of stress and emotional challenges due to their limited experience and exposure to the demands of the profession. This lack of experience can lead younger teachers to turn to emotional coping strategies as a primary means of managing stress and navigating the complexities of the teaching environment.

In addition, there is a significant difference in terms of the Pedagogical Knowledge and the Age of Practice-Teachers. This means that the 22-year-old Practice-Teachers got the highest mean of 4.06, while the 29-year-old respondents gained 3.60. This means that coping strategies in terms of pedagogical knowledge are mainly being used by Practice-Teachers at the age of 22. With that, they understand that fundamental teaching methodologies, classroom management, and practical experience are essential for

refining their skills over time. According to Alufohai and Ibhafidon (2015), the younger teachers between the ages of 21 and 34 were more effective in communication, classroom organization, and competence.

The result also shows that there is a significant difference in terms of the Content Knowledge and the Age of the Practice-Teachers. Given the table, the 22-year-old Practice-Teachers got the highest mean of 3.96, while 29-year-old respondents gained a 3.30 mean. This revealed that coping strategies in terms of content knowledge are used mainly by 22-year-old Practice-Teachers. This shows that young educators are typically active and passionate, which increases their level of satisfaction in their internship. This makes them foster their mastery of the subject matter because of their motivation and enthusiasm. According to the study of Liu et.al (2018), for individual young teachers, the degree of career satisfaction directly influences their working enthusiasm. Thus, the primary driver behind the future growth of educational institutions is the next generation of teachers.

Next, there is a significant difference in terms of the emotional and sex of the Practice-Teachers. Specifically, based on the sex of the respondents, males got the mean of 3.64 while females got 3.87. With that, it can be concluded that females got the higher mean and utilized more emotional coping strategies. This indicates that females may have higher emotional intelligence or better emotional regulation skills than males. This also suggests that the female respondents have developed more effective coping mechanisms or have access to better support systems for managing their emotions. According to Tchounwou and Mazur (2022), female students rated emotion-focused coping strategies higher than male students.

Lastly, there is a significant difference in terms of socialization and specialization of the Practice-Teachers. Based on the specialization of the respondents, the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Physical Education, Health, and Music got a mean of 4.60, while the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English got 4.19. With that, it can be concluded that BSE PEHM got the highest mean, and they utilized more coping mechanisms in terms of social. It may be due to the nature of the major since social interaction in this area of specialization is not more verbal but more in the form of gestures and movements. Thus, making social mechanisms more extensive. According to Nasri et al. (2021), most educators concentrate their Practice on standard gestures, specifically gaze and body language; they were noted and deemed safe as essential. When teaching physical education, these gestural components in the classroom build and uphold the safety principle.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the results of the study:

1. The majority are 22 years old, aligning with the expected age for student interns. The data also confirms the continued female dominance in the teaching profession. English remains the most preferred specialization, reflecting its perceived career opportunities and importance in education. Additionally, the study highlights the

increasing integration of technology in teaching, with laptops and smartphones being the primary tools for instructional tasks. Overall, these results emphasize the evolving characteristics of future educators, their academic preferences, and their adaptability to modern teaching methods.

2. In challenges faced by Practice-Teachers at Urdaneta City University, revealing significant physical, emotional, financial, and academic-related difficulties. Physical and emotional challenges were the most prominent, with concerns about classroom management, fatigue, and work-life balance affecting their teaching experience. Financial difficulties also posed a challenge, particularly in managing unexpected expenses. Social challenges, though less pronounced, highlighted the need for improved communication strategies.

In terms of academic-related challenges, Practice-Teachers encountered difficulties in applying diverse teaching strategies, demonstrating subject mastery, and integrating advanced technologies into instruction. While they had access to modern teaching tools, the effective use of technology and content delivery remained areas for improvement.

These findings emphasize the importance of providing targeted training, mentorship, and institutional support to equip Practice-Teachers with the skills and resilience needed for professional success. Strengthening these areas can enhance their overall teaching competency and readiness for future educational roles.

3. The study concludes that practice teachers at Urdaneta City University frequently utilize both personal and academic coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges of their internship. Social coping emerged as the most relied-upon personal strategy, emphasizing the importance of strong relationships with students, mentors, and family. Mentorship also played a crucial role in emotional coping, while financial coping strategies indicated a preference for self-reliance.

In terms of academic coping, pedagogical strategies were the most commonly used, particularly effective communication techniques. Content knowledge strategies, such as using instructional videos, also proved beneficial, while technological coping strategies indicated a general familiarity with digital tools but highlighted the need for continuous skill development.

The findings underscore the significance of a well-balanced approach to coping, integrating social, pedagogical, content, and technological strategies. Strengthening mentorship, financial management, and technology training can further enhance the ability of practice teachers to adapt to challenges and improve their overall teaching effectiveness.

4. Regarding the areas where the null hypothesis is rejected, practice teachers in different education specializations face distinct physical and emotional challenges influenced by the subjects they teach and their teaching methods. Physical challenges vary by specialization, with subjects like physical education requiring greater physical exertion. Emotional challenges also differ based on the subject matter, such as conveying abstract concepts in mathematics or fostering creativity in the arts. Additionally,

specialization impacts social dynamics among practice teachers, as diverse knowledge and perspectives shape interactions within educational settings. To address these challenges, practice teachers must possess both content expertise and refined pedagogical skills, enabling them to navigate the complexities of teaching in diverse contexts.

5. The null hypothesis is also rejected concerning age, as it influences how practice teachers cope with the physical and emotional demands of the profession. Younger individuals often rely on agility and energy, while older teachers emphasize endurance and resilience. Life experiences shape coping mechanisms, with older teachers exhibiting more effective strategies due to greater wisdom and emotional regulation skills. Specialization further impacts social coping, as subject-specific support is crucial, leading practice teachers to seek guidance from colleagues within their respective disciplines.

Additionally, gender norms and societal expectations influence emotional coping strategies, shaping how practice teachers manage stress and seek support. To enhance well-being, tailored resources and support systems should be provided. Pedagogical coping strategies also evolve with experience and professional development, allowing experienced teachers to develop more effective approaches to content-related challenges. They refine instructional methods and deepen their understanding of curriculum and assessment practices. Continued support and professional development opportunities are essential for enhancing pedagogical skills throughout a teaching career.

Conversely, in the remaining areas, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Recommendations

On the basis of the outcomes of this study, the following are suggested recommendations to improve the internship experience and professional growth of practice teachers at Urdaneta City University. The recommendations have been grouped according to institutions and individuals' responsibilities.

For Teacher Education Institutions and Internship Host Schools:

1. Augmenting Physical and Emotional Support

1.1 Enact wellness programs, including physical fitness training and stress management workshops, to assist practice teachers in coping with fatigue and emotional stress.

1.2 Offer ergonomic classroom arrangements, including rest areas, to reduce physical stress due to long-standing periods.

2. Financial Support and Management Training Strengthening

2.1 Investigate scholarship schemes, internship allowances, or financial literacy programs to assist practice teachers in coping with unforeseen expenses.

2.2 Incorporate hands-on financial management workshops as part of pre-internship training to impart practice teachers with resource allocation and budgeting skills.

3. Pedagogical and Content Knowledge Development Enhancement

3.1 Highlight experiential training in varied teaching methods, classroom management, and curriculum adjustment in teacher education programs.

3.2 Offer topic-specific review sessions, peer mentoring, and subject-specific training, especially in intricate subject matter, to fill content knowledge gaps.

4. Technological Training and Resource Enhancement

4.1 Incorporate extensive training on contemporary education technology, such as learning management systems, digital educational tools, and interactive content production, into preservice teacher training programs.

4.2 Arrange for internship host schools to allow practice teachers access to necessary instructional technologies and furnish ongoing support for troubleshooting and infusion of digital tools.

5. Developing Social Support and Mentorship Programs

5.1 Enhance mentorship programs by assigning practice teachers to experienced cooperating teachers for regular guidance and emotional support.

5.2 Establish robust professional learning communities between practice teachers and faculty to foster collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and overall teaching confidence.

6. Tailoring Support Based on Specialization and Demographics

6.1 Create tailored interventions for varied areas of specialization. For instance, physical education students might need physical endurance drills, whereas science and mathematics students might need models for breaking down complex ideas.

6.2 Utilize gender-sensitive and age-sensitive coping methods to ensure every practice teacher receives sufficient support addressing their needs and experiences.

7. Promoting Continuous Professional Growth

7.1 Provide regular professional development workshops, seminars, and certifications to assist practice teachers after their internship, enabling them to sharpen their pedagogical skills and content knowledge.

For Individual Practice Teachers:

8. Developing Personal Coping Strategies

8.1 Practice self-care activities, including exercise and relaxation methods, to cope with physical and emotional stress.

8.2 Obtain guidance and mentorship from cooperating teachers and colleagues to improve emotional resilience and teaching competence.

9. Enhancing Financial Management

9.1 Use budgeting and resource management skills to effectively manage financial difficulties.

9.2 Obtain financial support via available scholarship programs or part-time employment if the need arises.

10. Enhancing Teaching Techniques and Technological Flexibility

10.1 Improve pedagogical techniques continually by pursuing training sessions and using varied teaching methods.

10.2 Improve technological proficiency by utilizing educational tools, online tutorials, and step-by-step instructions to properly incorporate technology in teaching.

11. Creating Professional and Social Support Networks

11.1 Build strong connections with students, peers, and mentors to develop a supportive pedagogical climate.

11.2 Engage in professional learning communities and collaborate with other practice teachers for information sharing and trouble-shooting.

Through the implementation of these recommendations, teacher education institutions and practice teachers can maximize resilience, readiness, and general effectiveness, which will ultimately lead to better education quality in the 21st century.

INTERVENTION MEASURES TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES FACED BY PRACTICE TEACHERS

Introduction:

This intervention plan is developed based on a descriptive-quantitative study that investigated the challenges and coping mechanisms of practice teachers. It aims to address the significant physical, emotional, financial, social, and academic difficulties faced during their internship experience.

Objectives:

- To identify and understand the specific challenges encountered by practice teachers.

- To propose evidence-based interventions that enhance teaching effectiveness, well-being, and preparedness.
- To develop support systems that align with the diverse needs of practice teachers across different specializations, genders, and age groups.

Challenges Encountered	Intervention Measures
1. Physical fatigue and stress due to extended hours of teaching and standing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enact wellness programs including physical fitness training and stress management workshops. - Provide ergonomic classroom arrangements and rest areas. - Encourage self-care practices such as regular exercise and mindfulness activities.
2. Emotional strain from classroom management and work-life balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide emotional coping workshops focused on resilience and regulation. - Strengthen mentorship by assigning experienced cooperating teachers for emotional support. - Encourage peer-sharing and regular debriefing sessions.
3. Financial difficulties from transportation, resources, and daily expenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement scholarship schemes, internship allowances, or stipend programs. - Conduct financial literacy and budgeting workshops as part of pre-internship training. - Guide interns to seek part-time work or community financial aid where applicable.
4. Difficulty applying diverse teaching strategies in class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include experiential training and microteaching simulations during coursework. - Provide pedagogical workshops on differentiated instruction, inclusive education, and active learning strategies. - Encourage reflective teaching journals and peer feedback.
5. Challenges in demonstrating subject mastery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize content-focused review sessions and subject-specific mentoring. - Offer supplemental tutorials and instructional resource banks. - Develop instructional scaffolding for complex topics (especially for Math, Science, and English).

6. Ineffective integration of technology in lesson delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct intensive workshops on digital pedagogy, LMS usage, and multimedia content creation. - Ensure access to teaching technologies in internship schools. - Assign tech mentors and provide step-by-step guides for troubleshooting digital tools.
7. Social adjustment issues and limited communication skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct seminars on interpersonal communication and professional collaboration. - Build strong professional learning communities among interns and faculty. - Encourage collaborative lesson planning and group reflection sessions.
8. Specialization-specific physical/emotional demands (e.g., PE, Math, Arts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide customized interventions such as endurance training for PE majors or content simplification models for Math and Science. - Assign mentors from similar specializations for contextual support.
9. Age-related differences in coping mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer age-sensitive strategies: energy-focused routines for younger interns, and resilience-building techniques for older ones. - Leverage the life experience of older interns to mentor younger peers.
10. Gender-based emotional coping influenced by societal expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote gender-sensitive workshops to address stereotypes in stress management. - Encourage open dialogue about emotional well-being regardless of gender.
11. Inadequate pedagogical development over time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide post-internship professional development, certifications, and workshops. - Encourage lifelong learning and subscription to teaching networks or education forums.
12. Limited access to peer or mentor support networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Institutionalize mentorship programs and assign consistent cooperating teachers. - Foster regular peer consultation, observation, and reflection sessions.

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